
Expressions of “Death” in Newspaper Obituaries: A Cultural comparison of Japanese and Bengali

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Abstract:

Death remains a culturally sensitive and often taboo subject, with many languages exhibiting a reluctance to use the word directly. However, for death notices in newspapers the word, death or the verb, ‘to die’ is indispensable. Cultural norms as reflected in capturing this very linguistic choice thus makes an interesting study. This paper is an attempt to shed light on death euphemisms seen in newspaper obituaries and contrast the expressions for Japanese and Bengali language. It is a cross linguistic approach to understand the cultural underpinnings of how death is perceived and referred to. A corpus of 60 randomly selected obituaries from each language was analyzed to identify patterns of metaphorical mapping and cultural coping strategies embedded in language.

Keywords- Death euphemisms, Obituaries, Cultural norms, Metaphor, Cognitive linguistics

1.Introduction:

Cultural taboos surrounding language are found in nearly every society, often persisting even in contexts shaped by scientific and technological advancement. The term, *taboo* is believed to originate from the Polynesian word *tapu*, which denoted sacred or prohibited rituals, as observed and recorded by British explorers. These explorers’ diaries were later translated into multiple languages, and the word *taboo* entered global lexicons—stripped of its original religious and ritualistic meanings and reduced to a more general notion of social prohibitions or “don’ts.” Among these linguistic taboos—encompassing topics such as sexuality, bodily functions, and excretion—terms related to death and dying are among the most pervasive. As Hughes (2000) notes, death remains a universal and inescapable human experience, making its linguistic treatment both culturally significant and widely studied.

Death is a universally sensitive and often unsettling topic, prompting the use of euphemistic expressions across languages. As a concept that marks the irreversible end of human existence, it evokes fear and discomfort. To cope with the emotional weight of bereavement and to make sense of the unknown, people frequently rely on linguistic strategies—what may be termed “linguistic safeguards”—to refer to death in a more indirect and socially acceptable manner. Euphemisms for death thus emerge at the intersection of language, emotion, and cultural norms.

As Allan and Burridge (2006) observe, death is often perceived as “an unknown, something to be avoided, and something that is reasonable to fear.” This anxiety, rooted in the finite nature of life, is reflected in the wide range of lexical alternatives that serve to soften the starkness of death-related language. From the perspective of conversational politeness, euphemistic

expressions are not only a means of emotional buffering but also function as markers of respect toward the deceased and the bereaved. Instead of directly stating that someone “died,” more tactful alternatives such as “passed away,” “is no more,” “departed,” or “gone to a better place” are commonly used.

This paper is an attempt to compare euphemistic expressions related to death found in Japanese and Bengali culture as reflected in the phrases and words existing in the newspaper obituaries.

Both cultures in day today communication share the reluctance to speak of mortality, but obituaries have to but announce ‘death’. Interestingly, the term obituary originates from the Latin word, *obitus*, is a euphemism in itself that means departure. Obituaries are announcements of death and usually of two types- the informative and opinative. The former is about the death, the deceased or has the details of date and place for funeral and so objective in nature aiming to perform a locutionary function. The latter variety is more personal and thus subjective often performing a perlocutionary function of creating a favorable image of the deceased. It is the latter variety that is rich in figurative language. Obituary texts are genuine and authored by various authors of diverse backgrounds to understand how a language community addresses a sensitive topic as death. Obituaries reveal interesting information about language and its cultural moorings. Obituaries in the past have been studied to understand society’s cultural values through attributes of the deceased mentioned in the text and social construct of ‘good death’. The study of euphemisms has been undertaken by Allan and Burridge (1991) who demonstrate the verb, *die* occurred only once in their corpus of 536 obituaries collected from Australian newspapers.

There has been research on English metaphors mostly and contrastive study of metaphors used in English and Spanish (Marín-Arrese, 1996) and finding similarities in other European languages. Bultinck (1998) has created a classification of conceptualization of, wherein categorization was done to signify physiological effects of death, death as a movement, death as sleep, death as a loss, death as extinguished light etc. A later study by Fernandez (2006) concluded that the bulk of the euphemistic expressions were metaphors and his analysis was based on Conceptual Metaphor Theory that posits metaphorical mappings which the present article too shall employ. Malotki (1983) maintains, “Language provides a repertoire of coping mechanisms, of which metaphor is one of the most powerful and useful.” The three functions of metaphors are captured by Gibbs (1994), wherein the Inexpressibility hypothesis suggests that metaphors are a way to express difficult concepts, the Compactness hypothesis allow metaphors to transmit complex information in a compact way, and the Vividness hypothesis enables metaphors to enrich language by evoking vivid images.

The present article will first discuss the theoretical framework, situate concept of death in both the societies and then present the data sample collected, and finally discuss the differences and similarities.

2.Theoretical framework:

Allan and Burridge (1991) define euphemism as “A euphemism is used as an alternative to a dispreferred expression, in order to avoid possible loss of face: either one’s own face or, through giving offence, that of the audience, or some third party.” The theory of Politeness developed by Brown and Levinson (1987) is based on this ‘face’, which is “the public self-image that every member wants to claim for himself”. The question that arises is whose ‘face’ is being attended to

by the death euphemisms in obituaries. The euphemisms are in respect to the dead or the family left behind to cope with the event. By employing euphemistic expressions of death, the illocutionary force is minimized without changing the content of the message. Euphemistic expressions are linguistic manifestation of our cognitive systems and provide an understanding how a certain taboo is perceived and migrated.

Death euphemism in this article will not be treated merely as lexical device, but also explore the functional discourse. To base the discussion, a brief outline of Conceptual Metaphor Theory (Lakoff and Johnson, 1980) is important. A metaphor involves understanding one domain of experience in terms of a very different domain of experience. For example, when we say anger is fire, qualities of fire are known, so the mapping of anger an internal emotion is easier with a more tangible, accessible source concept. Gibbs (1994) highlights the significance of metaphor in our everyday thought. They are not distorted literal thought, but basic schemes by which people conceptualize their experience and their external world. Death is an unknown entity and the only way of perceiving it is through likening it to a known domain of experience like journey or sleep. Kövecses (2006) extends the conceptual metaphor theory onto a cultural frame supported by the language community.

For the present study, obituary examples were collected from leading Bengali newspapers and news websites in Japanese. Euphemisms about death were collected for a month from print copies of “*Bortoman*” and “*Anando Bajar Potrika*” for Bengali, while websites of “*Asahi Shinbun*” and “*Mainichi Shinbun*” for obituaries in Japanese were used for noting and generating corpus to analyze and draw conclusions. The number of examples collected in obituaries in both languages were not that exhaustive, as the study is more qualitative than quantitative. The source domains were identified and mapped to observe the areas of convergence and divergence in the two languages and the cultural underpinnings. Before the data set and findings are presented, it is useful to touch upon the notion of death in the two cultures.

3. Concept of death in Japan and Bengal:

Death is a universal truth, and belief systems surrounding it often reveal more similarities than differences across world languages. While the theme of death euphemisms has been widely explored in languages such as English, Spanish, Chinese, Arabic, and Korean, a noticeable research gap exists in contrasting two Oriental languages: Japanese and Bengali, particularly in the context of lexical choices used in obituaries. Although Bengali is also spoken in Bangladesh, this study focuses specifically on the variety of Bengali spoken in the Indian state of West Bengal, situated within a predominantly Hindu cultural framework.

3.1 Japan:

In Japan, there existed the concept of ‘*IMI*’ (忌み), quite similar to taboos of the West. *Imi-kotoba* (忌み言葉) are words that must be avoided in certain situations as the words are associated with bad luck, and instead a substitute word is to be used. A word that is used as a replacement is considered more polite and appropriate of societal rules.

In Japanese, there is a cultural reluctance to pronounce the number four as *shi* (四), since it is homophonous with *shi* (死), meaning "death," despite being represented by entirely different Chinese characters. To avoid this association, the alternative reading *yōn* is commonly preferred when referring to the number four. Japanese language has many homonyms and if a word is associated with something negative or less desirable, it is often substituted with an

alternative expression to avoid the risk of unfavorable connotations. The Japanese people believe in the spiritual power inherent in spoken words (*kotodama*) and hence are very careful while using certain words. People since olden times had the wisdom hence to fear the power of words and not speak words that bring bad omen. In Shinto shrines and Buddhist temples too, where spoken words or sutras (*norito*) had the absolute power, the very mention of words like death, blood, grave, illness etc. were considered taboo as they defiled the sanctity of the place. The *Engi shiki*, an imperial document of 927, for the Saigu rituals lists the replacement words used in the most revered of Japanese shrines, the Ise shrine. They are categorized as the Inner seven taboos related to Buddhism for Ise was a pure Shinto shrine, and the outer seven taboos related to non-Buddhist terms. Amongst the non-Buddhist words, death is one such entity whose mere mention defiles the sanctity of the place. In the creation mythology of Japanese pantheon of gods too, the principal deity, Sun goddess *Amaterasu* is born as Izanagi washes his left eye to cleanse himself of the death pollution after his visit to the land of the dead. Life in Japan thereafter is a consequence of this cleansing of death pollutant. Japanese language too thus has plenty of words to substitute the verb, to die. The verb '*shinu*' is used when discussing in general as *hito wa shinu* (People die) and not about a specific individual. It may be also used for first person subject, but typically avoided for others out of politeness. As an ageing society with many senior citizens perhaps the thoughts around death and its linguistic manifestations are but part of their lives.

A dictionary about death titled, "*Shi ni matsuwaru nihongo jiten*" (Okuyama, 1997) lists many words and concepts related to death. In Japanese, a broad range of euphemistic expressions is used in place of *shinu* ("to die") in day-to-day conversation, reflecting cultural sensitivities surrounding death. These are regularly used in funeral speeches and postcard notices. Some common replacement phrases are as follows: -,

- 1) *Nakunaru* (To die -polite equivalent of pass away)
- 2) *Ano yo ni iku / yo o saru* (To go to the other world/ To leave this world)
- 3) *Iki ga taeru* (Breathing stops)
- 4) *Iki ga kireru* (Breathing stops)
- 5) *Iki o hikitoru* (To draw one's last breath)
- 6) *Eimin* (Eternal sleep)
- 7) *Shikyo* (To die- formal usage)
- 8) *Takai suru* (To go to another world)
- 9) *Okakureni naru / Hougyo* (To die for royalty)
- 10) *Seikyo* (To die- formal usage)
- 11) *Tsuchi ni kaeru* (Return to earth)
- 12) *Kiseki ni iru* (To enter death register)
- 13) *Hotoke ni naru* (To attain Buddhahood)
- 14) *Hone ni naru* (To become bone)
- 15) *Kami ni mesareru* (To be called by God, for Christians)
- 16) *Meido e tabidatsu* (To go to the other world)
- 17) *Bosuru* (To die- formal usage)
- 18) *Oujou suru* (To go to heaven)
- 19) *Fuki no kyaku to naru* (A visitor of no return)
- 20) *Mimakaru* (To pass away to the other world)

Yanagita Kunio (1937), a prominent name in Japanese anthropology also has discussed how the phrase, "*Hiroshima e itta*" or its variation "*Hiroshima e tabako o kaini itta*" is an *imikotoba* for death,

where Hiroshima is not a place name, but symbolizes the other world. It can be concluded that Japanese language has abundant euphemistic expressions.

3.2 Bengal:

Like any other culture, Bengalis too consider death to be *asauch* (defilement) and there exists a range of purification rituals steeped in religious beliefs and social customs. In Hindu tradition, the body is cremated to facilitate the soul's journey through the cycle of reincarnation. The mourning period is marked by prayers, ritual observances, and specific dietary restrictions, including the abstention from fish and meat. After this period, the family gradually returns to regular life, often symbolically marked by *matsyamukhi*—the ritual resumption of eating fish. Additional practices include refraining from cutting hair, trimming nails, or shaving, all of which serve as expressions of grief and respect for the deceased. These hardships are observed to honor the departed and to reflect the solemnity of the transitional phase.

The Bengali language too has a vast repertoire of euphemisms to mitigate the harsh reality of a person's demise. Instead of the simplistic verb, '*mora*' (to die), Sanskritized words like *mrityu*, *prayana* are employed that mitigate the harshness of direct blunt reference. A recent study by Ray (2023) on metaphors of death in Bengali language had words and expressions listed down by fifteen native informants. Some of the words as replacements to 'to die' in that study are as follows:

- 1) *Deho tyag kora* (To leave the body)
- 2) *Shesh nishash tyag kora* (To give up on breathing)
- 3) *Porolok gomon* (To go to the other world)
- 4) *Chiroshojjae shuye pora* (To sleep on the forever bed)
- 5) *Kalnidra* (Endless sleep)
- 6) *Chirobidae* (Eternal farewell)
- 7) *Gongajatra kora* (To embark on a journey to the Ganges)

There were also notable observations of how the English word, 'expire', has been borrowed by educated Bengali speakers, as well as the use of analogies from the game of cricket where death is metaphorically linked to a batsman getting out, leading to expressions such as "wicket down". Such borrowed or adapted terms serve to abstract the concept of death, thereby creating a distance between the signifier and stark reality it represents. Casual slang expressions like *potol tola*, similar in function to the English phrase, "kick the bucket" were also noted. The origin of *potol tola* may lie in discarding the deceased's old clothes (*paat*), later evolving through word play into a euphemism for death. Overall, the majority of expressions observed were metaphorical in nature, often framing death as a form of journey.

4. Obituaries in Japanese and Bengali newspapers:

Obituaries are formal announcements of death where information is shared about deceased's death details, arrangement details of funeral or memorial services, facilitate a shared sense of mourning and to strengthen community belonging. However, since name and personal details are there, the content verbatim is not suitable for quoting the same. For both Japanese and Bengali, a corpus was drawn out of the verb used to mean 'to die' to study death euphemisms for this study. 60 instances in each were listed to discuss the lexical usage and cultural differences.

4.1 Obituaries in Japan:

Majority of the Japanese newspaper obituaries had the expression *shikyo* (死去) formal expression of die), with a few exceptions of *seikyo* (逝去). The expression *shikyo* was used in both Asahi and Mainichi newspapers. Obituaries in regional newspapers were also checked to see if the information of death was this objective and formal and it was found, whether Fukuoka local newspaper or of Hokkaido, the verb, *shikyo suru* remained consistent. Only one example in the Hokkaido newspaper was noted where the verb, *oujou suru* (passing on to next life). The news headline of the demise of oldest Japanese national, Hayashi Okagi as reported on 28th April, 2025 also carried the word *shikyo*. Even for the recent demise of the Pope, though of a different religion, *shikyo* was used. Only for Emperor's demise news in 1989, the special expression, *hougyo* (崩御) was used, reserved for monarchy. *Koukyo suru* and *Shukekyo suru* were also used earlier for other high-ranking officials in the Imperial family, but are now obsolete.

Seikyo was another expression noted in obituary corpus from newspaper as a deviation from the usual *shikyo*, when the deceased was not a relative and from the outer circle where respectful words were required. Though as detailed in Section 3.1 a vast range of words and expressions exist in Japanese, it was interesting to note that obituary texts were very objective in nature and euphemistic expressions were not observable. The obituaries focused on facts and emphasis on objectivity, *kyakkan houdou* or objective journalism being a characteristic of newspapers. Obituaries in Japan mostly had to adhere to a specific template with word limit concerns.

Though the objectivity is retained in newspaper, social traditions compel that in funeral speeches words duplicated such as *masumasu*, *tsugitsugi*, *tabitabi*, *kasane gasane* are to be avoided as they invite more misfortunes. Care is taken to avoid words such as *kieru* (to disappear), *ochiru* (to fall) that evoke a sense of loss.

4.2 Obituaries in Bengal:

In the corpus created for obituaries the maximum usage to replace *maru jawa* (to die) was *proyan* (formal expression) originating from Sanskrit *prayana*, which means departure. Unlike obituaries in Japan, many variations were noted in the corpus collected over a month, where death is seen as a journey and even referred to as *mohaprosthan* (the great departure). Many of the obituaries had mentioned the date of birth as *aasha* (coming) and the date of death as *jawa* (going), implying the visit of the soul to this world.

The other expressions noted were as follows: -,

- 1) *Chole jawa* (To go away), The destination is not mentioned but signifies passing away and a journey into the unknown.
- 2) *Amritloke jatra koreche/ Amritloke chole geche* (To go to the land of elixir)
Amrit is a Sanskrit word that signifies nectar of immortality and this expression would hope for no more ordeals of rebirth as *moksha* (liberation from cycle of life and death) is upheld in high esteem in the Hindu tradition
- 3) *Shorge chole jawa* (To go to heaven)
- 4) *Na pherar deshe chole jawa* (To go to a land of no returns)

- 5) *Lokantore chole jawa* (To go away to end of this world)
- 6) *Ihojgot chere jawa* (To leave this world) / *Porolok gomon* (To go to the other world)
- 7) *Aankhir aarale chole jawa* (To go beyond the eyes). The visible form is lost is signified in this expression. This ceasing to be visible is also captured with the expression *tirodhan* (concealment)
- 8) *Chironidrae ghumer deshe jawa* (To be in eternal sleep-in land of sleep)
- 9) *Tarar deshe chole jawa* (To go to the land of stars)
- 10) *Sbrikerishnor aashroye chole jawa* / *Golok dhame chole jawa* (To go to where Lord Krishna resides)

The last, 10th one was also about journey but with religious connotations in the Vaishnavite tradition. It is to be noted that Bengal has both Vaishnavite (sect that follow Lord Vishnu or Krishna) and the Shaivite (sect that follows Lord shiva) traditions. In the Shaivite tradition, Lord Shiva as the destroyer signifies the end, and his consort, Goddess Kali is seen as the ferocious Mother figure that envelops followers in her embrace at the time of death. The collected obituaries over one month did not have any explicit referencing to the Shaivite tradition. In Hinduism, where death is a mere stage in the cycle of rebirth, it is a comforting idea to perceive death as a return journey to the divine from which new life form originates.

It was noted that of the 60 examples collected, 55 had the connotations of death being a journey. Three examples were of being invisible to the eye, one that referred to death as '*kalo oddhaye*' (black chapter) and one of '*Pancha bhoote bilin howa*' (to fade into the five elements, i.e., earth, water, fire, air and ether, the building blocks of the body and universe).

5. Observable differences in Japanese obituaries and Bengali obituaries:

Japanese obituaries were more for information and objective with near zero variation in the verb, to die observable. There was no photograph of the deceased or details about the emotions of the bereaved family. Grief in Japan was personal and not exhibited in public. Post war modernization and objectivity maintained by newspaper as a mass media instrument may also be plausible reasons of such formal language bereft of any emotion. Japanese philosophy of *mujōkan* (impermanence) may be a factor too. The Buddhist teaching of *shōgyō mujō* transmitted over years in Japan helps its people realise that change is the only permanent truth. The physical existence too must cease at some point and death is to be embraced by all humans. Folktales in Japan, use the verb *shinu* (to die) without any embellishments. Except for funeral speeches where face needs of audience and the deceased are to be attended to for politeness's sake, the Japanese don't feel the need to use death euphemisms in obituaries.

In Bengali obituaries, the tone is often conversational, as if addressing the departed soul directly. Euphemisms for death are used as a mark of respect for the deceased. Additionally, obituaries in India are typically paid notices, which results in variations in length and content depending on the family's preference and means. Unlike Japan ones, the obituaries are much more personalized, emotive and even have photograph of the deceased. The range of euphemisms too is varied with bulk of them denoting a journey undertaken by the soul in continuation to the journey called life. The tone is not always hinging on sadness as there are imageries of reunions with other deceased family members too referred to.

Another interesting point that sets apart obituaries in India are the song quotations as dedications. Of the 60 examples collected, 13 of them had song lines cited. The Nobel laureate, Rabindranath Tagore is known for his philosophical and poignant poems/songs that resonate with the bereaved family. In several of Tagore's poems in Gitanjali, life and death take on the roles of a bride and bridegroom and their meeting signifies the beginning of the journey towards union with the supreme being. The lyrics of the Tagore songs that were noted in the obituaries were however more for the deceased vis-à-vis the members left behind.

- 1) “*Tumi robe nirobe bridoye momo*” (You will reside silently in my heart)
- 2) “*Noyon shommukhe tumi nai / Noyoner majhe niyecho je thain*”
(You are not in front of my eyes / You have taken the place in my eyes)
- 3) “*Bhora thak smriti sudhae bidayer patrokhan?*” (Filled with the nectar of memories let the farewell goblet remain)
- 4) “*Ki phul jhorilo bipulo ondhokare*” (What flower was it that dropped in the darkness deep)

In addition to Tagore's songs, there were some contemporary soulful song lyrics such as *Amar Bitor Bahire Ontore Ontore aacho tumi bridoy jurey* (You are in my whole being from inside to outside Your presence is entwined in heart) by Bangladeshi poet Rudra Mohammad Shahidullah that were used as quotations. Sanskrit *shlokas* from sacred Hindu texts like the *Bhagavad Gita* were similarly used, reflecting how obituaries draw not only on euphemisms but also on metaphors rooted in music and spiritual healing to cope with loss. In comparison to Japanese obituaries, Bengali ones often appeared more emotively expressive and layered with personal sentiment.

As a future task it remains to be seen if nature of obituaries has changed or will change with time as the society evolves further. Since death remains a constant, obituaries in this way give an interesting peak into the *Shiseikan* (Perception of life and death) in both the cultures and necessitates further cross linguistic studies.

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